

Gender Differences in Career Maturity of Madrasah Aliyah Student

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Abstract— This study purposed to find difference of career maturity between male and female students in Madrasah Aliyah. Sample of this study are 310 students from one of the Madrasah Aliyah in Medan City-Indonesia, and taken using incidental sampling techniques. The data were analyzed using the independent sample *t*-test. The results show there was no differences in career maturity, neither male nor female student. The findings of this research could be a reference to further research about career maturity, and career problem solution of Madrasaah Aliyah students.

Keywords— Career maturity, gender, Madrasah Aliyah student.

I. INTRODUCTION

Career maturity is an individual's ability to determine the right career choice, be aware of the things needed to make career decisions, and be able to be realistic and consistent when deciding career choices (Crites in Levinson, Ohler, Caswell, & Kiewra, 1998). If students are not show career maturity, such as deciding a career without knowing their potential and information about corporate world, it will allow dissatisfaction against their job (Muntamah & Ariati, 2016). Therefore, career maturity is important for Madrasah Aliyah students.

Madrasah Aliyah is an Islamic Public High School that organized by the Ministry of Religion, which is Islamic character is reflected in Islamic Education lessons, creating a religious environment, and animating all subjects with Islamic teachings (in the Minister's decision Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 370, 1993). The Islamic lessons in Madrasah Aliyah are developed into 5 subjects, these are Arabic, Fiqh, Al-Quran Hadith, Akidah Akhlak, and Islamic Cultural History.

A number of Islamic lesson and general lesson are taught by linking the teaching of Islam, as well as the Islamic school environment, make them have extensive knowledge about Islam. The extensive religious knowledge can be affected in career maturity of Madrasah Aliyah students, based on finding research by Marliani (2013), that good knowledge about religion will make individuals have plans in their career that they pursue. Thus, Islamic knowledge make students of Madrasah Aliyah planning their careers, because they understand the Islamic teaching say that earning a living is one of worship to Allah SWT. It proves a research by Satria and Wahyuni (2015), where is 60.5% of students in Madrasah Aliyah in Banda Aceh have strong confidence in their career.

Through FGD activity (Sunday, 6th January, 2019), the researcher had taken 11 Madrasah Aliyah students in Medan, and found that some of them had several alternative choices in their major and desired careers, where they realized that they would grow up and have to fulfill their needs by working, as

the word of Allah SWT in Quran Surah At-Taubah verse 105 concerning Allah's command to work. Even so, it turns out that of all students are able to determine their career choices steadily. Some of the students in FGD activity were known to experience obstacles in deciding their career choice, such as confusion and hesitation in making decisions regarding lecture majors and careers that were in accordance with their abilities

Furthermore, the survey results obtained by Putra (2015) using inventory of Student Problem Identification (IMS), found a number of career problems for Madrasah Aliyah students. The problems are: (1) have not chosen and have not definite follow-up education plan; (2) lack of information about further education to be entered; (3) confused in making career goal; (4) worry about income of future work is does not provide sufficient; (5) lack of understanding how to choose the right job; (6) lack of understanding of the influence of education on success and career later, (7) pessimistic because of the intense competition in entering further education; and (8) the anxiety of becoming unemployed after graduated.

Career problems of Madrasah Aliyah students actually show the level of their career maturity. Many factors can affect career maturity, one of them Santrock (2014) mentions is gender, where Super and Overstreet (in Osipow, 1983) classify it into biosocial factors. In the concept of development, it is clear that women reach each stage of the development phase faster than men (Papalia, Olds, & Feldman, 2009). It indicates that women reach career maturity faster than men.

Many studies have revealed differences in male and female career maturity, such as Alam's research (2013); Marpaung and Yulandari (2016); Nafeesa, Aziz, and Harjdo (2015); and Rahmi and Puspasari (2017), who found that women had a higher career maturity than men. Patton and Creed (2001) explain that women can be more open about their career information. Therefore, women can be more mature than men in terms of career development. However, different results were found by Momin and Chetry (2016), that no differences in career maturity between men and women.

Based on the problem above, the researcher wants to see the level of career maturity in Madrasah Aliyah students, and the differences career maturity between male and female students in Madrasah Aliyah.

II. OBJECTIVE AND METHODS

The main purpose of this study was to determine the level of career maturity in Madrasah Aliyah students. The subjects of this study were 310 students, consist of 114 male students (36.8%) and 196 female students (63.2%). Sample were taken

using non-probability sampling methods and incidental sampling techniques.

Data of the study was obtained through a scale of career maturity that has been tested for reliability and validity, and demographic data in the form of gender of students. The career maturity scale is based on four dimensions of career maturity according to Savickas (2013), namely concern, control, curiosity, and confidence. Career maturity scale consists of 15 item statements with a reliability level of 0.841. This scale used a Likert scale model with five alternative answer choices: 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (neutral), 4 (agree), 5 (strongly agree). Scores for each item correspond to the answers given by the subject. However, on some items in negative statements, the opposite score applies.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Result of his study showed that Madrasah Aliyah students generally have career maturity in middle category, as many 232 people (74.8%). Meanwhile, students with career maturity in high category, as many 78 people (25.2%), and there are no students (0%) who have career maturity with low category. This result is similar to the findings of Mulyani, Setiawan, and Hidayat (2014) on Madrasah Aliyah students in Cikarang, where the student has career maturity in the middle category. Furthermore, the description of career maturity can be seen in more detail through each dimension of career maturity, which can be seen in this table:

TABEL I. Overview of dimensions of career maturity.

Dimension	Mean			SD	Meaning
	Hypothetical	Empirical	Residual		
Concern	12	14.75	2.75	2.60	High
Control	6	6.14	0.14	1.54	Middle
Curiosity	18	20.61	2.61	3.16	Middle
Confidence	9	10.79	1.79	1.80	Middle

Savickas (2013) states that students who do not have career concern, are characterized by the absence of future plans, being pessimistic, and resigning to their future. In this study, Madrasah Aliyah students have high categorized career concerns (see Table I). Thus, it can be said that Madrasah Aliyah students have career planning in the future. Meanwhile, the dimensions of control, curiosity, and confidence are still relatively middle, So Madrasah Aliyah students can be given self-development related to these three dimensions.

Furthermore, to find out whether the hypothesis is accepted or not, the independent sample t-test is tested, after the assumption test has been fulfilled before. The results of the comparative test show that there is no difference in career maturity, both for male students and female students ($t=0.108$, $p>0.05$). These results are similar to findings obtained by Birol and Kiralp (2010); Nuswantoro and Warsito (2013); Jatmika and Linda (2015); and Ratnaningsih, Kustanti, Prasetyo, and Fauziah (2016).

As explained earlier that Madrasah Aliyah students get a lot of Islamic studies and animate all general subjects with the teachings of Islam, so that they have extensive knowledge about the religion of Islam, where this knowledge affects the

career maturity. In the teachings of Islam, humans are ordered to seek sustenance by working. However, Islam also says that the position of the mother is more important than the father, as the hadith of the Prophet Muhammad, when asked who we should serve first, then the Prophet answered "your mother, your mother, your mother, then your father". It indicates that women have a very important role in their families. Therefore, career planning for female students in Madrasah Aliyah is done by considering its role as a mother and wife, so that their career maturity tends to be the same as male students.

IV. CONCLUSION

Results of this study indicate that there are no significant differences in career maturity, both for male students and female students in Madrasah Aliyah. In addition, this study also revealed the career maturity of Madrasah Aliyah students tends to be in the middle category. Furthermore, looking at the dimensions of career maturity, it is known that students have a dimension of concern in the high category, while the dimensions of control, curiosity, and confidence are in the middle category.

The results of this study could be guidance for further investigations on career maturity and intervention of career maturity improvement, especially for Madrasah Aliyah students.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. M. Alam, "Study of gender difference in career maturity of rural and urban students in India," *Global Journal of Scientific Researches*, vol. 1, issue 1, pp. 19-25, 2013.
- [2] C. Birol and Y. Kiralp, "A comparative analysis of the career maturity level and career indecision of the first grade high school students," *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 5, pp. 2359-2365, 2010.
- [3] D. Jatmika and Linda, "Gambaran Kematangan Karir pada Mahasiswa Tingkat Akhir," *PSIBERNETIKA*, vol. 8, issue 2, pp. 185-203, 2015.
- [4] E. M. Levinson, D. L. Ohler, S. Caswell, and K. Kiewra, "Six approaches to the assessment of career maturity," *Journal of Counseling and Development*, vol. 78, pp. 475-482, 1998.
- [5] R. Marliani, "Hubungan antara Religiusitas dengan Orientasi Masa Depan Bidang Pekerjaan pada Mahasiswa Tingkat Akhir," *Jurnal Psikologi*, vol. 9, issue 2, pp. 130-137, 2013.
- [6] D. N. Marpaung, & N. Yulandari, "Kematangan Karir Siswa SMU Banda Aceh Ditinjau dari Jenis Kelamin dan Jenis Sekolah," *Jurnal Psikolamedia*, vol. 1, issue 2, pp. 311-324. (2016).
- [7] Menteri Agama Republik Indonesia. (1993). *Keputusan Menteri Agama Republik Indonesia Nomor 370 Tahun 1993 tentang Madrasah Aliyah*. Retrieved from http://simpuh.kemenag.go.id/regulasi/kma_370_93.pdf.
- [8] N. S. C. Momin and G. Chetry, "Influence of gender and locale on the career maturity of students in degree colleges," *International Journal of Informative and Futuristic Research*, vol. 3, issue 10, pp. 3910-3918, 2016.
- [9] S. Mulyani, T. I. Setiawan, and D. R. Hidayat, "Kematangan Karir Siswa Madrasah Aliyah Negeri (MAN) Cikarang," *Insight: Jurnal Bimbingan dan Konseling*, vol. 3, issue 2, pp. 103-108, 2014.
- [10] Muntamah and J. Ariati, "Hubungan Antara Kelekatan Terhadap Teman Sebaya dengan Kematangan Karir pada Siswa Kelas XI SMK Negeri 1 Trucuk Klaten," *Jurnal Empati*, vol. 5, issue 4, pp. 705-710, 2016.
- [11] N. Nafeesa., A. Aziz, and S. Hardjo, "Gambaran Kematangan Karir Ditinjau dari Jenis Kelamin pada Siswa Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan dan Sekolah Menengah Umum Perguruan Panca Budi Medan," *Psikologi Konseling*, vol. 7, issue 2, pp. 21-33, 2015.
- [12] J. T. Nuswantoro and H. Warsito, "Perbedaan Kematangan Perencanaan Karir pada Mahasiswa Laki-laki dan Perempuan Ditinjau dari Keaktifan dalam Organisasi Kemahasiswaan," *Character: Jurnal Penelitian Psikologi*, vol. 2, issue 1, pp. 1-9, 2013.

- [13] S. H. Osipow, *Theories of Career Development, 3rd Edition*, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, 1983.
- [14] D. E. Papalia, S. W. Olds, and R. D. Feldman, (Edisi 9). *Human Development (Psikologi Perkembangan)*, Jakarta: Salemba Humanika, 2009.
- [15] W. Patton and P. A. Creed, "Developmental issues in career maturity and career decision status," *The Career Development Quarterly*, vol. 49, pp. 336-351, 2001.
- [16] R. T. Putra, "Upaya Meningkatkan Kemampuan Pemilihan Karier Siswa Melalui Konseling Kelompok dengan Pendekatan *Trait Factor* pada Siswa Kelas X MIA 2 MAN 1 Yogyakarta Tahun Ajaran 2014/2015," *E-Jurnal Bimbingan dan Konseling Edisi 11 Tahun ke-4*, pp. 1-9, 2015. Retrieved from <https://www.e-jurnal.com/2016/07/upaya-meningkatkan-kemampuan-pemilihan.html>.
- [17] F. Rahmi and D. Puspasari, "Kematangan Karir Ditinjau dari Jenis Kelamin dan Jenis Sekolah di Kota Padang," *Jurnal RAP (Riset Aktual Psikologi)*, vol. 8, issue 1, pp. 24-35, 2017.
- [18] I. Z. Ratnaningsih, E. R. Kustanti, A. R. Prasetyo, and N. Fauziah, "Kematangan Karir Siswa SMK Ditinjau dari Jenis Kelamin dan Jurusan," *Humanitas: Jurnal Psikologi Indonesia*, vol. 13, issue 2, pp. 112-121, 2016.
- [19] J. W. Santrock, *Adolescence, 15th Edition*, New York: McGraw-Hill Education, 2014.
- [20] B. Satria and S. Wahyuni, "Self-Efficacy Keputusan Karir pada Siswa Madrasah Aliyah," *Idea Nursing Journal*, vol. 6, issue 3, pp. 10-18, 2015.
- [21] M. L. Savickas, *Career Construction Theory and Practice*, Dalam S. D. Brown & R. W. Lent (Editor), *Career Development and Counseling: Putting Theory and Research to Work, 2nd Edition* (halaman 147-183), Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, 2013.